

SOME INFORMATION NEEDS FOR AGRICULTURE

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ABSTRACT

With the mission of “Helping People Help the Land,” the Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) provides products and services that enable people to be good stewards of the Nation’s soil, water, and related natural resources on non-federal lands. Aerial and satellite imagery in the form of digital orthoimagery is the geospatial foundation of the NRCS mission. Imagery is essential to delivering conservation technical assistance to landowners, to data gathering for the Soil Survey Program and the National Resources Inventory (NRI), to program management efficiency, and for carrying out disaster response. NRCS uses both aerial (film and digital) and satellite imagery in meeting its mission responsibilities. One-meter resolution, natural color imagery is used for Soil Survey Program field mapping and digitizing soils boundaries and in the Customer Service Toolkit Geographic Information System (GIS) for conservation planning at all service centers. Very high (3-6 inch) resolution photography is used to collect natural resource data at the NRI’s 800,000 sample points and to monitor Wetlands Reserve Program (WRP) easement compliance. One-meter resolution pansharpened satellite imagery is the choice for areas where aerial collection is difficult because of weather, distance from the contiguous U.S., and cost. In the operational use of imagery, NRCS strives to maximize purchases through cost-sharing agreements and new technologies.

Index Terms— Photography, satellites, image processing, image analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Imagery is mission critical. Aerial and satellite imagery in the form of digital orthoimagery (imagery mathematically corrected to enable accurate measurement and location) is the geospatial foundation of the NRCS mission. It is essential to delivering conservation technical assistance to landowners, to data gathering for the Soil Survey Program and the National Resources Inventory (NRI), to program

management efficiency, and for carrying out disaster response and homeland security responsibilities.

Imagery used by NRCS is divided into two types: aerial imagery and satellite imagery.

- Aerial imagery, collected on film or by digital sensor from aircraft
 - NAIP (National Agricultural Imagery Program) [1] - One-meter resolution, natural color imagery is used for Soil Survey Program field mapping and digitizing soils boundaries and in the Customer Service Toolkit Geographic Information System (GIS) for conservation planning at all service centers. This imagery is critical to NRCS’ ability to respond quickly in natural disasters (e.g., soil and site evaluations for debris and animal carcass disposal following Hurricane Katrina).
 - USDA Small Area Photography Contract - Very high (3-6 inch) resolution photography is used to collect natural resource data at the NRI’s 800,000 sample points and to monitor Wetlands Reserve Program (WRP) easement compliance.
- Satellite imagery - One-meter resolution is the imagery of choice for areas where aerial collection is difficult because of weather, distance from the contiguous U.S., and cost. Satellite imagery is used for soil surveys, the NRI, and the Customer Service Toolkit, primarily in the Pacific Basin, Hawaii, and Alaska. This type of imagery costs more than aerial imagery and is licensed for NRCS use only.

2. ACQUISITION AND FUNDING

NRCS partners with other federal agencies to obtain aerial imagery from the Farm Service Agency’s Aerial Photography Field Office (APFO) and satellite imagery from Foreign Agriculture Service (FAS) contracts. These partnerships provide cost savings yet ensure flexibility to

meet specific agency needs and were organized specifically to prevent duplication of effort and unnecessary spending. For 2006, NRCS invested over \$14 million in imagery acquisition. Of this, \$2.8 million was for NAIP photography, but this investment leveraged access to nearly \$30 million of imagery for our field offices.

3. CURRENT INITIATIVES

3.1. Conservation Technical Assistance [2]

Since 1935, the Natural Resources Conservation Service (originally called the Soil Conservation Service) has provided leadership in a partnership effort to help America's private land owners and managers conserve their soil, water, and other natural resources. To assist in providing technical assistance, NRCS employees often prepare a conservation plan containing a map and/or written record of the management decisions and the conservation practices that are in use or planned. Participation in NRCS programs is voluntary. The conservation plan combines the farming or ranching skills of the operator with the science-based knowledge of the NRCS. The plan contains:

- an aerial photo or diagram of the fields,
- a list of management decisions,
- the location of and schedule for applying new conservation practices,
- a soil map and soil descriptions,
- information sheets explaining how to carry out the specific management decisions,
- a plan for operation and maintenance of practices, if needed.

Conservation plans today are prepared with the Customer Service Toolkit Geographic Information System on a backdrop of one-meter resolution digital orthorectified imagery. The orthorectified imagery used comes from NAIP.

3.2 National Resources Inventory [3]

The NRI is a statistical survey of the natural resources on non-federal land in the United States, about 75 percent of the total land area. The inventory is conducted by NRCS in cooperation with the Center for Survey Statistics and Methodology at Iowa State University. The NRI collects data on land cover and use, soil erosion, prime farmland soils, wetlands, habitat diversity, selected conservation practices, and related resource attributes. Data are collected from the same 800,000 sample sites in all 50 States, Puerto Rico, the U.S. Virgin Islands, and some Pacific Basin locations. Prior to 2003 the NRI was conducted on a 5-year cycle using a combination of field visits and available archived aerial photography. Now NRI data are collected in 3 NRCS Remote Sensing Labs using 3-6 inch resolution aerial photography specifically acquired for the inventory. Using a modified sampling scheme, photos are acquired over about 70,000 NRI area segments each year. The

photos, primarily 1:7,920 scale, are provided to NRCS as natural color film positives and as 40 micron (600 dots per inch) photogrammetric scans. NRCS uses customized photogrammetric software to register the scans to historical imagery. NRI data elements on the registered scans are visually photo interpreted and measurements recorded using onscreen digitizing on a GIS workstation.

Related to the NRI is the Conservation Effects Assessment Project (CEAP) [4] which began in 2003 as a multi-agency effort to quantify the environmental benefits of conservation practices used by private landowners participating in selected U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA) conservation programs. The grazing lands component of CEAP will quantify the environmental effects of conservation practices used on non-federal rangeland, pastureland, and grazed forests. Currently field visits and aerial imagery are being used to collect data for this project.

3.3 Wetland Reserve Program [5]

WRP is a voluntary program that provides financial incentives to land owners to restore, protect, and enhance wetlands. USDA purchases an easement that limits future use of the land, but the land remains in private ownership. NRCS is tasked to inspect the easements annually for violations. Currently, onsite annual inspections are transitioning to aerial photo interpretation using 1:7,920 scale natural color film. Photos are scanned, orthorectified, and mosaicked. Data are visually collected on a GIS. Suspected violations are forwarded to State Offices for onsite verification.

3.4 Soil Survey Program [6]

NRCS is the lead agency on mapping soils on non-federal lands in the United States. The backdrop for both published and web-based soil surveys is one-meter resolution orthorectified digital image from the National Digital Orthophoto Program [7] or NAIP.

3.5 Disaster Response

In the wake of a disaster, NRCS has the lead responsibility for:

- burial of animal carcasses (NRCS coordinates with the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) and USDA – Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service (APHIS) on this task),
- testing of soils for salt concentration,
- analysis of cultural sites for debris removal including National Historic Register Sites,
- locating, prioritizing, and contracting for the removal of debris from streams and canals (done through the Emergency Watershed Protection (EWP) [8] program),
- debris assessment in agricultural areas,
- providing assistance to landowners.

NRCS uses historical NDOP and NAIP imagery, as well as imagery acquired in the wake of the disaster, for these purposes.

3.6 Satellite Imagery

Although airborne systems capture the majority of image data used by NRCS, satellite imagery occupies a important niche within agency operations. Usually aerial acquisition is difficult and expensive in the Pacific Basin, Hawaii, and Alaska. In these areas, one-meter pansharpened satellite imagery is a suitable replacement, especially if the data are acquired with a cost share agreement.

In the Western United States, the Soil Survey Program is beginning to use Landsat and Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) satellite imagery for soil survey updating and premapping. Premapping helps soil scientists identify areas which require more detailed mapping. In addition, NRCS continues to make limited use of Landsat for land cover/land use classification and invasive species mapping.

4. CURRENT AND FUTURE IMAGERY AND TECHNOLOGY NEEDS

USDA programs are under pressure to work more effectively, and remote sensing is a technology enabling NRCS to provide better and timelier information. Although NRCS continues working with farmers and ranchers at the local level, remote sensing is allowing some work to be done at other levels in the organization. To continue the improvements, NRCS users of remotely sensed data would benefit from:

- More timely imagery for conservation planning. Currently NAIP is on a 5-year refresh cycle. A new effort called Imagery for the Nation (IFTN) [9] is targeting an annual refresh cycle with the possibility of 4-band imagery.
- The NRI is a film based acquisition program. Efficiencies could be gained by using 4-band, digital cameras and providing that imagery already orthorectified. Studies need to be conducted to determine if automated change detection software can assist in the data collection process.
- The CEAP has determined that the resolution of NRI-like photography is too coarse to eliminate field data collection. CEAP needs 3-cm or better resolution, 4-band imagery.
- WRP, like the NRI, would benefit from 4-band, digital orthorectified imagery. Additionally, techniques need to be explored to automate the mosaicking of WRP easement photos.
- The Soil Survey Program prefers to use leaf-off imagery for mapping and publication. The NAIP imagery being provided today is leaf-on. The Soil

Survey Program would benefit from periodic national leaf-off orthoimagery.

- The Soil Survey Program is beginning to use Landsat and ASTER satellite imagery for premapping in the Western United States. Remote sensing is particularly valuable for updating existing soil maps. For example, high resolution digital orthoimagery and elevation data, in conjunction with multispectral imagery, provide powerful tools for delineating individual soil components previously mapped as complexes. In addition, remotely sensed data provide useful layers in quantitative predictive soil-landscape models.
- For disaster response, NRCS would benefit from post-disaster imagery acquired in the rural landscape.
- Several NRCS programs including the NRI and Soil Survey Program need national high resolution elevation data to better delineate drainage and slope. Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (IFSAR) is useful in sparsely vegetated terrain, but less so in dense vegetation. Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) is a technology that can provide NRCS' high resolution elevation data needs, but costs are high.
- NRCS' use of medium resolution satellite imagery has fallen in recent years because of the failure of the scan line corrector on Landsat 7 and FAS' change to the Advanced Wide Field Sensor (AWiFS) for global crop production analysis. NRCS supports the Landsat Data Continuity Mission and launch of the next generation Landsat satellite.

5. CONCLUSION

NRCS makes extensive use of aerial imagery, and limited use satellite imagery, in fulfilling its mission. Technology advancements in remote sensing and cost sharing on data acquisition improve the value of NRCS' imagery investments.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] USDA Aerial Photography Field Office, 2006. NAIP Information Sheet. http://www.fsa.usda.gov/Internet/FSA_File/naip_final_2006_updatep.pdf
- [2] NRCS Conservation Planning Assistance website. <http://www.nrcs.usda.gov/programs/planning/>
- [3] NRCS National Resources Inventory website. <http://www.nrcs.usda.gov/technical/NRI/>

[4] NRCS Conservation Effects Assessment Project website. <http://www.nrcs.usda.gov/technical/NRI/ceap/>

[5] NRCS Wetland Reserve Program website. <http://www.nrcs.usda.gov/programs/wrp/>

[6] NRCS Soil Survey Program website. <http://www.nrcs.usda.gov/programs/soilsurvey/>

[7] National Digital Orthophoto Program website. <http://www.ndop.gov/>

[8] NRCS Emergency Watershed Protection website. <http://www.nrcs.usda.gov/programs/ewp/>

[9] National States Geographic Information Council, Imagery for the Nation Flyer. http://www.nsgic.org/hottopics/iftn/imagery_forthe_nation.pdf